

CHALKONES. STUDIES IN THE CLAISEN-SCHMIDT CONDENSATION

BY DURGA NATH DHAR*

The effect of three substituent groups, viz., hydroxyl, methoxyl and methyl, substituted in the aldehyde component and hydroxyl in the ketone component, on the Claisen-Schmidt condensation has been studied.

The chalkones were prepared according to the procedure of Schraufstatter and Deutsch (*Chem. Ber.*, 1948, 81, 489). The procedure consists in the addition of about 50% aqueous KOH to benzaldehyde and acetophenone derivative in ethanol and heating at 60° for 2 hours on a water bath. The chalkones were isolated in the usual way. The %yield of various chalkones, obtained under identical conditions, are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Ketone.	B.	Hydroxy-B.			Methoxy-B			Dimethoxy-B		Hydroxy-methoxy-B		Methy -		
		<i>o</i> -	<i>m</i> -	<i>p</i> -	<i>o</i> -	<i>m</i> -	<i>p</i> -	2:3-	3:4-	4:3-	2:3-	<i>o</i> -	<i>m</i> -	<i>p</i> -
Resaceto-phenone	41.4	4.5	28.6	..	81.9	33.9	46.9	69.0 } 71.8 }	33.2	..	10.9	60.5	50.9	64.1
<i>o</i> -Hydroxy-acetophenone	64.6	34.6	69.0	23.6	85.6	60.9	69.5	61.2	64.4	19.9	48.6	48.5 } 49.5 }	52.6	66.7
Acetophenone	‡	63.5	47.7*	53.3	86.1	83.7	88.6	85.6	76.2	48.8	73.0	‡	‡	‡

B represents benzaldehyde.

‡ Abnormal condensation occurs.

* Side reaction takes place.

N.B. - Condensation failed to occur with resorcyaldehyde.

As no definite generalisation can be drawn to cover all the experimental data recorded in Table I, only the significant conclusions arrived at are given :

In general, the introduction of OH-group, in either of the reacting molecules, retards or sometimes completely inhibits the Claisen-Schmidt condensation. Examples are the condensation of resacetophenone or *o*-hydroxyacetophenone with salicylaldehyde and resorcyaldehyde.

Nevertheless, the presence of OH-group, particularly in the ketone component, prevents the formation of undesirable products. Thus resacetophenone and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone condense normally with benzaldehyde and isomeric tolylaldehydes to yield the respective chalkones; on the other hand, the interaction of acetophenone with the above mentioned aldehydes does not lead to the formation of chalkones* under the experimental conditions employed. Formation of chal-

* Present address : Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur.

kones in the above condensation can, however, be secured by using a milder concentration of alkali and carrying out the reaction at a lower temperature (Kohler and Chadwell, "Org. Syntheses", Vol. II, 1922, p. 1; Weygand and Schacher, *Ber.*, 1935, **58B**, 227).

Replacement of the OH-group by either methyl or methoxy (in the aldehyde component) results in increase in yield of the chalkone.

The author thanks Dr. J. B. Lal for interest in this work and the Government of India, Ministry of Scientific Research and Cultural Affairs, for the award of a senior research scholarship.

H. B. TECHNOLOGICAL INSTITUTE,
KANPUR, U.P.

Received March 26, 1960.